

1

2 **The Twin Transition Puzzle: Can City Governments Align Digital and** 3 **Sustainability Regimes?**

4

5 Abstract

6 Cities are increasingly expected to harness the potential of the “twin transition”—the coupling
7 of sustainability and digital transitions—to govern complex socio-technical systems. Yet, little
8 is known about how this multi-regime transition unfolds in urban contexts or how it is
9 coordinated by city governments. Drawing on 82 interviews and extensive document analysis
10 across ten European cities, this study finds that the two transitions remain weakly integrated
11 within and beyond municipal administrations. Our findings suggest that effective coupling
12 requires not only comprehensive horizontal and vertical coordination but also the
13 development of organizational capabilities tailored to the demands of the twin transition.

14

15 Keywords: digitalization; sustainability; twin transition; multi-regime interactions;
16 coordination; transition governance; organizational capabilities

17

18 **Introduction**

19

20 It is becoming widely acknowledged that addressing the sustainability challenge necessitates
21 coordinated transitions across multiple socio-technical systems and regimes (Andersen and
22 Geels 2023; Kanger and Schot 2019). Part of this recognition pertains to a widespread
23 assumption that combining digital and green innovations is key to achieving sustainability
24 transitions (Creutzig et al. 2022; Lema and Perez 2023; Santarius et al. 2023). This integration,
25 often referred to as the “twin transition” (TT), refers to “how the dynamics and strength of
26 the digital transition of society affect the green transition of society, and how these two
27 transitions mutually influence each other and should be combined in the coming years”
28 (Dæhlen 2023, 12). The twinning imperative suggests that the coupling of these two
29 transitions can influence the direction and speed of long-term structural changes in various

1 sustainability-relevant socio-technical systems and regimes (Mäkitie et al 2023; Andersen and
2 Markard 2024).

3

4 So far, the phenomenon of the TT remains understudied (John et al., 2022; Pel, 2024; Sareen
5 and Haarstad, 2021). Not only do we know little about how the digital and green transitions
6 are conceptually related, but also if and how exactly they reinforce each other (Andersen et
7 al., 2021; Mäkitie et al., 2023). Nevertheless, public sector organizations are expected to play
8 a significant role in enabling and coordinating the TT (Gao, 2025; Lema and Perez 2023;
9 Kovacic et al 2024; Meijer 2024; Ministerial Declaration 2021). At the same time, many of the
10 sustainability challenges need to be addressed at the urban level (Ehnert et al 2018; Wolfram,
11 2016), as “cities are the locations where most of the (un)sustainability issues find their origin”
12 (Loorbach 2017, 160). Local government organizations are believed to be in key position to
13 solve these place-based sustainability transition challenges by creating and nurturing new
14 markets, initiating and facilitating transition networks, enabling new social practices, and
15 leading by example as they reform public service provision (Bianchi et al 2024; van der Heijden
16 2019). In Europe, cities have been the main venue where combining the environmental and
17 digital goals have been explicitly promoted (Kovacic et al., 2024). Although the very concept
18 of TT rose to prominence with the European Green Deal (EGD) in 2019, “the coupling of
19 environmental and digital aims could already be seen in the “smart, sustainable and inclusive
20 growth” trope of 2010, mainly under the smart city rhetoric” (ibid., p. 2255).

21

22 However, recent studies analysing cities as central loci of socio-technical transitions have
23 voiced a concern whether cities have the transformative capacity needed for systemic socio-
24 technical changes and to what extent the realities match the expectations (Turnheim et al
25 2020). For a (twin) transition to happen, government organizations need not only to figure out
26 what to do (García Casañas and Kovacic, 2025; Rogge and Reichardt 2016), but also how to do
27 it (Gao 2025; Borrás et al 2024; Braams et al 2022). For the latter, governments need high-
28 level problem-solving and coordination capabilities (Loorbach 2010; Mayne et al 2020), but
29 there seems to exist very limited thinking on public administration enabling the sustainability
30 transition (Toonen 2010; Pollitt 2015; Biesbroek et al 2018). Concurrently, there exists limited
31 knowledge about how the public sector can coordinate across different system boundaries
32 and bring together the digital and green transitions (Gao, 2025; García Casañas and Kovacic,

1 2025) and what public sector strategic and organizational adjustments are needed for the TT
2 (Meijer 2024).

3

4 This paper focuses on how the European city governments coordinate the multi-regime
5 interactions between the digital and sustainability transitions. The aim of the paper is to
6 inform the TT debates by providing novel empirical insights into the emerging TT coordination
7 practices in the urban context and what kind of organizational capabilities are needed to
8 create and sustain the synergies between the two transitions. Following Loorbach (2010), the
9 paper conceptualizes three generic spheres of state action in TT: transition governance,
10 transition strategies, and innovation projects as transition niche experiments. To understand
11 how city governments enable these actions, the paper evokes the concept of organizational
12 capabilities (Borras et al. 2024, Braams et al 2022, Kattel and Mazzucato 2018; Lember et al
13 2018) that are manifested in routines and practices through which these strategic aims,
14 policies and experiments are legitimized, implemented and institutionalized.

15

16 The following research question guides our study: How do cities couple the sustainability and
17 digital transitions? To facilitate the research process, we additionally formulated four inter-
18 related sub-research questions (SRQ):

19 SRQ1: How do cities participate in the TT governance?

20 SRQ2: What strategies and policies do cities adopt for the TT?

21 SRQ3: What innovation practices and activities do cities initiate for the TT?

22 SRQ4: What kind of skills and resources do cities mobilize for the TT, and how?

23

24 The article aims at making three key contributions. First, the article provides original empirical
25 evidence on how European city governments understand, strategize and practice the TT.
26 Second, we propose and make use of a novel framework to understand the role public sector
27 organizational capabilities play in coordinating the TT. Finally, the paper offers practical
28 insights into how various types of multi-regime interactions and associated capabilities can
29 enhance the potential for city governments to further integrate sustainability and digital
30 transitions.

31

1. Conceptual background

1.1. Twin transition as a multi-regime interaction

There is an increasing expectation that integrating sustainability and digital innovations can influence the rate and directionality of sustainability transitions in various socio-technical systems and regimes from energy and mobility to AI development (Mäkitie et al., 2023; Creutzig et al., 2022; John et al., 2022; Lema and Perez, 2023). This synergistic effect can be interpreted as emerging through mechanisms like those observed in multi-regime interactions (Konrad et al., 2008), which refers to ‘different types of couplings and resource flows between systems’ (Andersen and Markard, 2024). These interactions can happen, for example, through the flow of materials, finances, energy and other resources (functional coupling), shared technologies and institutions leading to new organizational units or complementary innovations (structural coupling), or cross-system discourses that legitimize new actions (rhetorical coupling) (ibid.). Crucially, neither digital nor sustainability represent a specific socio-technical system or regime per se but can be considered as meta-regimes (or paradigms) that provide different directionalities and meta-rules for various other systems and regimes (Kanger et al 2024).

The interaction dynamics between the digitalization and sustainability transitions are complex and multidirectional. The two transitions evolve in parallel (Mäkitie et al., 2023) and have significantly different internal evolutionary logics (Kovacic et al., 2024; Stirling, 2024). While the digital transition has emerged through capitalistic techno-economic evolution and has a powerful endogenous motor of change (strong spillover effects), the current green transition narrative (e.g., European Green Deal) has emerged largely out of political demand and has relatively weak automatic spillover effects (Lema and Perez 2023). Furthermore, digitalization can either support sustainability transition or hinder it. On the one hand, digitalization enables cross-sectoral interaction by, for example, integrating transport charging and electric grid management systems (Sareen and Haarstad 2021), creating radically de-centralized niches such as commons-based electricity systems (Giotitsas et al., 2022), or through providing new options such as digital passports for understanding products’ lifecycle costs (Creutzig et al

1 2022). On the other hand, efficiency gains by digitalization may reinforce the dominance of
2 unsustainable technological trajectories (Andersen et al 2021). High-level digital capabilities
3 are also key in enabling big digital platform companies to further extend their power and
4 activities into mobility, health, energy and other key sustainability-relevant domains
5 (Andersen et al 2021), while influencing people’s opinions, social practices and consumption
6 behaviour (Creutzig et al, 2022). Not to mention that the material footprint of producing and
7 consuming digital technologies is already significant and increasing rapidly (Al Kez et al 2022;
8 Itten et al. 2020; Jones 2018).

9 1.2. Coordination of the twin transition

10
11 Although calls for active government involvement in transformative transitions (TT) are
12 longstanding, there remains limited clarity on how governments can effectively facilitate and
13 coordinate the necessary structural changes (Kovacic et al., 2024; Faggian et al., 2024).
14 Addressing this requires distinguishing not only between vertical and horizontal dimensions
15 but also between internal and external coordination. The vertical dimension involves
16 translating political goals across cultural, institutional, and operational spheres, and aligning
17 multi-level stakeholders (Loorbach, 2010; Lazarevic et al., 2022). Horizontally, coordination
18 entails integrating diverse sectors and engaging external actors—such as businesses, regions,
19 and citizens—since cities often lack the resources to act independently as transition agents.
20 This coordination supports both instrumental goals and the legitimacy, implementation, and
21 scaling of TT. Internally, coordination is essential to align fragmented and decentralized
22 government structures. Coordination can be understood both as an outcome—where policies
23 are coherent and non-redundant—and as a process involving hierarchical, market-based, or
24 network-based mechanisms to align stakeholder efforts (Bouckaert et al., 2010; Sarapuu &
25 Lember, 2015).

26
27 Following the logic of multi-regime interactions, TT coordination can be conceptualized as an
28 effort to foster communication between otherwise autonomous transition regimes. This may
29 involve traditional public sector approaches to strategic and transition management, seeking
30 digital technologies that support sustainability goals (Creutzig et al., 2022; Muench et al.,
31 2022). Governments may mobilize configurational ICTs to reshape generic technologies—such
32 as deploying smart meters to influence energy systems (van Summeren et al., 2021)—or to

1 create, disrupt, or maintain institutions within socio-technical regimes, for instance, through
2 pilot projects in autonomous public transport (Soe & Drechsler, 2018). Alternatively,
3 coordination may aim to predefine and implement a specific TT model by establishing co-
4 creation platforms, new institutional instruments, and experimental spaces. This approach
5 could respond to calls for moving beyond technocratic visions of TT, addressing second-order
6 environmental and socio-economic impacts of digitalization (Meijer, 2024). A third
7 perspective sees governments leveraging the rhetoric or rules of one transition to legitimize
8 actions in another. Recent studies highlight rhetorical coupling as a key strategy used by the
9 European Commission and member states to reconcile economic and sustainability agendas,
10 thereby addressing legitimacy challenges in democratic governance (García Casañas &
11 Kovacic, 2025; Kovacic et al., 2024).

12

13 1.3. Public administration capabilities for the twin transition coordination

14

15 Effective state action in (twin) transitions depends not only on political bargaining and policy
16 choices but also on the administrative structures and capabilities that enable policy
17 implementation (Janssen et al., 2023; Borrás et al., 2023; Karo & Kattel, 2018). This includes
18 designing internal organizational arrangements, managing external relationships, and steering
19 public organizations and networks (Fernández-i-Marín et al., 2025) that align with government
20 roles and tasks in transition governance (Braams et al., 2022). Capabilities are based on
21 learned, repeatable and reliable routines supported by individual skills, contextual requisites
22 and other building blocks (Dosi et al 2000). At their core, capabilities reflect how organizations
23 mobilize and coordinate tangible (e.g., financial, physical) and intangible (e.g., human,
24 cultural, political) resources (Amit & Schoemaker, 1993; Borrás et al., 2024). Central to these
25 tasks are coordination resources—such as authority, information, bargaining, power, and
26 shared norms—that underpin effective governance (Bouckaert et al., 2010).

27

28 Loorbach (2010) suggests that transition governance has three key spheres of activities: long-
29 term cultural change (the level of landscape), dominant structures and institutions (the level
30 of regime), and concrete innovation projects and action (the level of niches). Integrating these
31 three spheres requires reflexive capabilities (i.e. learning from projects and renewing strategic
32 goals, structures and institutions to ensure the direction of long-term cultural change) (ibid.).

1 Whereas the landscape level processes tend to be long-term, chaotic and difficult to control
2 for any actor, it is the two other levels where the organizational capabilities become central.
3 The pathways to the regime change result from stakeholders' strategic aims, their
4 institutionalized practices and how the socio-technical change processes are coordinated and
5 enacted between societal actors (ibid.). Public sector organizations may develop explicit
6 approaches where they legitimize their political choices and lay out the policies for enabling
7 as well as destabilizing various socio-technical regimes. Here the state capabilities are key,
8 which relate to, for example, how public sector is structured, how autonomous public
9 institutions are vis-à-vis other societal stakeholders and whether the government has access
10 to relevant resources to coordinate the strategic actions (Kattel et al., 2025).

11
12 The niche level is the key sphere of innovation activities that function as a source of novelty
13 for the socio-economic transitions. Public sector organizations can themselves act as
14 innovators in TT pilot projects and experiments as they provide public services, while often
15 they act as enablers of innovations initiated by societal or economic actors via regulation,
16 subsidies or networking (Kattel et al. 2018). The organizational capabilities that underpin both
17 the regime and niche level activities are based on various routines such as analytical, planning,
18 coordination, evaluation, and participation (Karo and Kattel 2018).

19
20 The transformative action often assumes change in the organizational resource-base and
21 capabilities (Kattel et al. 2025). If operational capabilities enable organizations to get things
22 done (e.g., implement a TT project) then dynamic capabilities enable reflexivity and act upon
23 the operational capabilities (e.g., routines that deliberately enable to enhance the ability to
24 couple the digital and sustainability innovations). As such, the dynamic capabilities are
25 intrinsically related to what Borrás et al. (2024) refer to as organizational transformative
26 capacity "in terms of how it engages in institutional and system-wide transformation, by
27 purposefully performing specific roles exercising change agency, and by deploying and
28 developing its dynamic skills when mobilizing the internal and external resources at its
29 disposal".

30
31 To summarize, the recent transition and innovation policy literatures have attempted to
32 conceptualize various government transition roles and necessary capabilities at the policy and

1 administrative levels. However, from the perspective of TT, the government coordination of
 2 multi-regime interactions has been overlooked. Effective TT assumes coordinated action
 3 across different regimes, systems, organizations and units, which, in turn, depends on various
 4 organizational capabilities. We assume that since the two transitions evolve largely in parallel
 5 and with different direction and speed, the city governments do not actively engage with the
 6 landscape-level long-term TT visioning. Yet, since smart and sustainable city narratives
 7 dominate the current European and national policy discourses, we expect cities to have at
 8 least rhetorical strategies and policies in place that would facilitate the coordination between
 9 the digital and sustainable innovations at the organizational level. Correspondingly, we also
 10 assume cities to be active in experimenting with the twin innovations. We expect those
 11 innovations to affect the regime-level strategies and change only if supported by fit-for-
 12 purpose (dynamic) organizational capabilities.

13 2. Methodology

14
 15 The study follows the multiple case-study approach. Our aim is to explore and describe the
 16 emerging TT coordination patterns and related organizational capabilities across different
 17 socio-ecological realities (such as varying levels of adherence to green and digital transitions),
 18 size (from small towns to city-states), geographical contexts (the North-South climate axis)
 19 and administrative cultures. For this, we purposively selected 10 European cities as presented
 20 in Table 1.

21

22 **Table 1:** Overview of the studied cities

City	Status	Population	N of interviews
Barcelona (Spain)	Regional capital	1,6 million (M); 5,3M in province	9
Utrecht (Netherlands)	Regional capital	360 000; 1,37M in province	12
Hamburg (Germany)	City-state	1,9M; 5,4M in metropolis	5
Leuven (Belgium)	Regional capital	100 000; 1,19M in province	7
Rotterdam (Netherlands)	Municipality	650 000; 3.6M in province	8

Camden (UK)	Metropolitan borough	25 000; 8,6M in metropolis	11
Helsinki (Finland)	National capital	630 000; 1.58M in metropolis	10
Lund (Sweden)	Municipality	132 000	10
Tallinn (Estonia)	National capital	460 000; 610 000 in metropolis	7
Tartu (Estonia)	Municipality	93 000	6

1

2 The selected cities have all put the sustainability transition at the centre of their policymaking
3 and are considered as green transition leaders at the national or European levels (see
4 Appendix 1). The selection includes cities that are partners to the European Climate Neutral
5 and Smart Cities network, and cities that are not (Camden, Hamburg and Tallinn). Data for
6 analysis was collected in each city based on intensive interviewing (N=82), and desktop
7 research of strategic documents. Interviewing targeted civil servants with prominent roles in
8 digitalization, sustainability transition, innovation or strategic planning. After establishing first
9 contacts through publicly available data, snowballing technique was applied to expand the
10 circle of interviewees in each city. Interviews followed a common semi-structured protocol
11 that covered three transition spheres: transition governance, organizational strategies and
12 innovation experiments, as well as the organizational capabilities enabling the twin transition.

13

14 The interviews were conducted in February-November 2024. Parallel to interviewing,
15 researchers collected strategic documents and other materials regarding digitalization and
16 sustainability transition. The interviews and documents in each city were then analysed based
17 on a common protocol stemmed from the conceptual framework presented above. We used
18 the deductive thematic analysis approach (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane 2006) whereby
19 materials were coded following themes and concepts using NVIVO software. Corroborated
20 codes resulted in 10 city reports which were then compared and further condensed. The
21 comparative results were further validated by researchers familiar with each city.

22 3. Results

23 3.1. Tilting the landscape for multi-regime interactions

24 The domestic and international social, economic and technological macro trends regarding
25 sustainability and digitalization creates a landscape that influences the management of and

1 interactions between the sustainability and digital transitions. Our interviews show that the
2 landscape pressure to couple the two transitions is rather weak for the studied cities. Existing
3 European policy initiatives (such as NetZeroCities or Recovery and Resilience fund) are
4 considered as “an opportunity to integrate both transitions more meaningfully” (emphasised
5 by interviewees from Barcelona) but are perceived as too scarce and underwhelming to count
6 as drivers for getting engaged in long-term TT governance.

7 Digitalization and sustainability pressures are perceived as parallel developments, resulting in
8 cities aspiring leadership roles in one or another (e.g. Lund as the global leader of sustainability
9 transition or Tallinn as the global leader of digital transition). Consequently, in the studied
10 cities, shaping the long-term goal formulation and norm-setting in sustainability and
11 digitalization transitions are separated. The sustainability and digital transitions are “born
12 from different places and are quite distinct” (Barcelona) and are not “the most obvious
13 combination” (Utrecht).

14 The parallel nature of the two transitions is expressed by their divergent internal logic and
15 speed that shapes the strategic stance of the studied cities. Digitalization is mostly perceived
16 as a tool to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery and to involve citizens
17 in urban affairs. Although some cities showcase their digitalization efforts (e.g. Barcelona,
18 Tallinn), the position of cities is rather “catching up” and “capitalizing on” with the fast pace
19 of digital developments, than “driving” or “shaping” it. The sustainability transition, on the
20 other hand, is internalized in the strategic goals in terms of climate emergency and is directly
21 shaped by national contexts (e.g., its legitimacy, legal frameworks, funding, competencies).

22 The representatives of cities display a dual stance towards shaping the long-term coupling of
23 the transitions. On the one hand, most of the city representatives demonstrated their interest
24 in the topic and thought it would be worthwhile to bring these transitions together more
25 proactively. On the other hand, many respondents voiced their scepticism towards the active
26 role of cities in twinning the transitions. This scepticism stems from either a more fundamental
27 or a more pragmatic reasoning. Fundamentally, sustainability “wins” were mostly seen as
28 stemming from non-digital areas such as restricting car access or changing energy production
29 (Barcelona, Tartu, Helsinki, Lund). Given the choice between investing “on the ground” vs “in
30 the digital”, the former prevails because “no politician wins by [stressing on] technology”
31 (Leuven) and “digitalization is not on the radar of politicians” (Utrecht). Civil servants also

1 pointed to noticeable risks of digitalization on public values (Barcelona, Utrecht), while some
2 others pointed out the importance of equity and justice within the TT (Rotterdam) and the
3 presence of fundamental conflict between the economic growth aspirations and sustainability
4 transitions (Hamburg). More pragmatically, due to the global scale and interconnectedness of
5 the transition challenges, the cities were not deemed to be the right venue of TT governance.

6 *And as I said, since these are both huge megatrends and topics, we approach it more*
7 *that they both need to be looked at separately and then need to have the connection*
8 *where the connection made sense, and the references where it makes sense, but to try*
9 *to tackle them entirely together would be overwhelming, because they are so complex.*
10 *(Policy officer at the Department on Digitalisation and IT, Hamburg)*

11 Overall, the city representatives were having difficulties in imagining the cities' role in the
12 wider cultural shaping of the TT debates. This results in a mostly inward-looking position of
13 the cities, whereby the more tangible TT narrative (and – as will be shown below – strategies
14 and actions) is confined to specific socio-technical systems and corresponding organizational
15 departments on the tactical and operational levels.

16 3.2. Coordination of multi-regime interactions on sectoral level

17 All the cities have developed domain-specific strategies for different socio-technical systems
18 where the integration of digitalisation and sustainable is addressed. Harnessing digital
19 technologies for emission reduction (and to a lesser extent biodiversity protection and
20 material use) are visible in the energy (Lund, Helsinki, Utrecht), transport (Barcelona,
21 Hamburg, Lund, Helsinki, Tartu), urban planning (Hamburg, Camden, Leuven, Lund, Helsinki,
22 Tartu, Utrecht), construction and circular economy (Rotterdam, Lund, Utrecht), and waste
23 management (Lund) domains. In each domain there is a plethora of ongoing projects which
24 combine digitalization and sustainability aims for achieving sectoral aims (more below). For
25 example, in Hamburg the Traffic Authority is developing a mobility strategy, focusing on
26 creating a comprehensive master plan for digitalisation. The primary objective of this strategic
27 approach is to encourage a "modal shift," nudging citizens towards more environmentally
28 friendly modes of transportation by 2030. The Mobility strategy document states: "The
29 strategic goals interlock to enable future-proof digital mobility that meets the needs of all
30 users while simultaneously minimising environmental impact".

1 Yet, the domain-specific strategies and initiatives do not contribute to overarching (city-level)
2 TT coordination nor the adoption of corresponding meta-rules. Cities recognize opportunities
3 in combining sectors and initiatives, but the strategic coordination encompasses such
4 complexities that it remains largely “opportunistic” (Camden, Leuven).

5 *You need to move up and down between the operational project level and the abstract,*
6 *strategic level. For that, you need a governance model, and you need to let it trickle*
7 *down to test it. The question is: can you move back and forth between operational,*
8 *tactical, and strategic levels like a yo-yo, constantly trying to connect the whole?*
9 *There's an interesting interaction there. [...] Only top-down doesn't work, only bottom-*
10 *up doesn't work either” (Program manager in the field of sustainability, Rotterdam).*

11 A recurring theme in merging digitalization with sustainability is the emphasis on datafication.
12 Digitalization is often framed as a means to enhance analytical and accountability capacities
13 in sectoral sustainability transitions—what can be termed the institutional use of data. For
14 instance, cities like Lund, Hamburg, and Helsinki provide sustainability data to citizens to foster
15 accountability, while civil servants in cities such as Tallinn and Tartu hope that transparent
16 data can bolster the legitimacy of green policies. However, despite these ambitions, officials
17 in Lund, Hamburg and Tallinn acknowledge the difficulty of linking digital interventions directly
18 to measurable reductions in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, as impacts may only become
19 evident over decades. Moreover, the benefits of non-digital interventions—such as phasing
20 out coal power in Helsinki—are often more immediate and tangible. In some cases, the
21 growing demand for increasingly granular data is seen as a form of “paralysis by analysis,”
22 delaying more fundamental policy decisions.

23 Second, data is used for achieving GHG emission reduction, biodiversity protection and other
24 sustainability goals to achieve efficiency gains. This can be interpreted as the instrumental use
25 of data. The application of this data takes various forms in terms of processes and outcomes.
26 Technology may be harnessed for GHG emission reduction through better engineering (e.g.
27 gathering data from district heating systems in Helsinki and optimizing its flows), towards
28 behaviour change and collaboration with citizens (e.g. using digital platforms for capping peak
29 energy reduction in Lund, Helsinki), or towards process and behaviour change inside city
30 administration (e.g. applying a new spatial planning narrative based on GIS in Lund).

3.3. Three types of niche-level innovation practices

As implied above, all the studied cities implement domain-specific projects which combine and experiment with digital and sustainability niche innovations. Based on the main driver and focus, these initiatives fall under three categories that we have named sustainability-driven, technology-driven and coordination-driven innovations (Table 3).

Table 3: Types of niche-level innovation practices in the studied cities

Sustainability-driven innovation	Technology-driven innovation	Coordination-driven innovation
Sectorial goals for achieving environmental sustainability motivates seeking for digital solutions	Novel technological opportunities are developed that address long-term sustainability goals	Bottom-up challenges in administrative processes trigger search for “twin” solutions
Example: data-based guiding of district heating flows in Helsinki	Example: self-driving cars in Tallinn	Example: energy communities in Lund

Reflecting domain-based strategizing, most TT innovation projects are driven by sustainability goals, particularly those tied to sector-specific carbon reduction targets. In response, civil servants actively seek digital solutions aligned with these ambitions—most notably in energy systems. Digitalization supports enhanced analytics (e.g., emissions data in Utrecht and Lund), operational efficiency (e.g., data-guided district heating in Helsinki), and citizen engagement (e.g., energy user interfaces in Helsinki and Lund). Urban mobility is another key area, with cities like Hamburg leveraging digital data to reduce GHG emissions. Sustainability goals also push public authorities into domains traditionally outside their regulatory scope, motivating experimentation with digital tools. Waste management and the circular economy exemplify this shift. As cities move beyond recycling to reducing material flows in consumption and construction, digitalization is expected to offer both instrumental tools (e.g., digital material cadastres in Utrecht) and interactional mechanisms (e.g., personalized digital engagement in Lund). However, such expansive transition practices remain limited, with most innovation still focused on incremental efficiency gains.

In contrast to sustainability-driven initiatives, many technology-driven innovations in cities are motivated by global competition to develop cutting-edge technologies—such as autonomous vehicles, drones, or digital twins. These projects are often loosely connected to cities’ immediate strategic goals and are typically supported by external funders like the EU.

1 Although motivated through sustainability aims, their contribution to concrete sustainability
2 outcomes, such as GHG reduction, remains ambiguous. Frequently led by specialized
3 innovation units or externally funded branches of city governments (e.g., Helsinki, Hamburg),
4 these initiatives often face challenges in institutionalization due to weak organizational
5 coupling. As a result, their goals may not align with sectoral priorities, limiting their systemic
6 impact.

7 *I think that most of the innovation projects now done with external funding are in the*
8 *innovation Horizon 3, like drones, advanced data, ecosystems. My opinion is that we*
9 *should focus on the Horizon 1, on the biggest problems that we are right now having in*
10 *our services, and [thus] bring the innovation near us, instead that somebody in a bubble*
11 *tries to fix future problems. (Strategy manager, Helsinki)*

12 Cities' experiences show that integrating digital technologies into sustainability governance is
13 a gradual process. The use of digital twins in Tallinn, Helsinki, and Lund illustrates this. While
14 all three cities have developed digital models incorporating green spaces and vegetation for
15 biodiversity planning, institutional uptake varies. In Tallinn, new GIS routines have yet to be
16 fully embedded, running parallel to older practices. In Helsinki, initial use was limited to
17 specialists, but iterative experimentation has broadened adoption across urban planning.
18 Lund demonstrates the most advanced integration, using digital twins to support a
19 collaborative planning paradigm that balances renewable infrastructure with biodiversity in
20 dense urban areas.

21 The third—and smallest—type of innovation in cities is driven by efforts to improve
22 organizational coordination. These initiatives often originate within units tasked with
23 collaboration or are catalysed by external funding and networks. Typically defined bottom-up
24 by civil servants, their goals may relate to either sustainability or digitalization. For example,
25 initiatives may seek to align energy and building departments around shared sustainability
26 objectives. These ideas undergo a process of interpretation and intermediation, during which
27 organizational goals, procedures, and technologies are critically examined and new models
28 proposed. This pragmatic, analytical approach fosters a reflective stance on the sustainability
29 impacts of digital technologies and encourages more integrated, context-sensitive innovation.

1 *I'm trying to help [my colleagues] not do stupid things. It's not only technology,*
 2 *optimization, but like business project process or rethinking the whole operations.*
 3 *That's always the platform. We don't just jump into a digital solution. We always try to*
 4 *take the step back. Because they often think, oh, I need an app. That's kind of the*
 5 *number one. We try to help them to really ask themselves, what is the real need?*
 6 *(Innovation expert, Lund)*

7 The CoAction “system demonstrator” in Lund is a good example of a project aiming to rethink
 8 energy infrastructure in the city through internal and external coordination. Internally, one of
 9 the goals is to combine virtual energy grids, DC-technologies, and building and energy
 10 departments for creating urban energy communities. Externally, since the participants predict
 11 that the goals in energy and mobility transformations would be contested by vested interests,
 12 they are including lobbying and networking as project activities.

13 3.4. Twin Transition Capabilities

14 To couple the two innovation fields means that the city governments need to combine two
 15 very different knowledge domains and resources bases commonly distributed across various
 16 internal and external organizational units. The experience of the studied cities points to
 17 several “ways of doing” that constitute as the key twinning capabilities (Table 4). Notably,
 18 considering the dynamic and unpredictable context of sustainable and digital transitions, the
 19 cities require dynamic capabilities to enable the constant adjustment of the organizational
 20 routines to the twinning challenge.

21 **Table 4:** Key capabilities for TT in city governments. Source: authors; the generic capabilities
 22 are synthesised based on Borrás et al. (2024), Braams et al. (2021) and Kattel et al. (2025)

Generic capability	Twin-specific practice	Examples
Exploring, sensing	Participation in twin networks	EU NetZeroCities mission (most cities)
	Creating or accessing new data to understand sustainability dynamics	The Climate Impact Monitoring System (Hamburg)
	Sharing data across departments for experimenting and ideating	Combining building material and waste management data for circular economy (Utrecht)
	Sharing data across sectors	Open data provision (Barcelona)
Repositioning, guiding	Citizen engagement to legitimize radical sustainable and digital change	Citizen assemblies, digital inclusion, mobilizing citizens' pressure (Camden, Barcelona, Hamburg, Leuven)
	Clear political preferences, pressure and support enables to agree on new TT foci and overcome barriers	NetZeroCities Climate Contract signed by political leaders

	Creation of TT policy and implementation space outside traditional policy domains	Missions (Barcelona, Camden, Rotterdam); innovation centres (Barcelona, Camden, Helsinki, Rotterdam); innovation teams (Lund); living labs (Leuven)
	Holistic management towards applying digitalization for sustainability goals	Strategy department's analysis and dedication to pragmatic application of digitalization in achieving sustainability goals (Helsinki)
	Formal domain strategies that guide multi-system couplings	Sectoral strategies (e.g. mobility, energy, circularity) that explicitly guide the uptake of digital solutions for achieving sustainability goals (Hamburg, Lund, Camden, Rotterdam)
Coordinating, collaborating	Coordination with policy stakeholders within the region and state	Regional collaboration in the Netherlands, Sweden and elsewhere
	Ecosystem engagement for local changes and up-scaling	Initiation of large local climate policy networks with private stakeholders (Barcelona, Hamburg, Lund)
	Mobilizing private finances to advance TT	Public-private financing (Barcelona, Camden)
	Using public procurement to induce TT in the private sector	Plan to update procurement guidelines for sustainable technologies (Camden)
Exploiting, accelerating	Continuous expansion of the use of digital tools for sustainability goals within the city government	Experimentation with Digital Twins that led to new planning practice and paradigms (Lund, Helsinki, Tallinn)
	New organizational structures that enable digital transformation for sustainability purposes	Reforming organizational structures in municipal energy and transport companies around data creation, management and use (Helsinki)
	New budgeting logic to drive sustainability transition	Climate budgeting (Barcelona)
	Up to date and interoperable digital infrastructure	Open data, regulatory sandbox, guidelines and economic support for sustainable business (Barcelona)
	Hiring in-house staff with skill-sets capable of bridging the two fields	Hiring waste management lead from digital sector (Lund)
Learning, reflecting	Data-informed sustainability decision-making	„Traffic light” system for sustainability goals (Lund)
	Creation of new staff positions to enable learning between projects	Redefining “project managers” into “strategists” (Lund)
	Continuous initiation of cross-domain projects targeting TT	Material cadastre for building materials and recycling (Tartu, Utrecht, Lund)
	Informal networking for cross-domain learning	Informal communication between sustainability, air quality, energy and GIS teams (Camden)

- 1
- 2 For the capabilities outlined above, cities rely on a bundle of skills and resources. In the
- 3 thematic analysis, five key groups were seen as crucial for coupling the two transitions:
- 4 knowledge, human capital, finance, digital maturity and coordination. Importantly, cities
- 5 acknowledge critical competence and resource gaps that makes it problematic to develop
- 6 adequate organizational support for the TT.

1 Developing and nurturing TT capabilities requires situated awareness of the synergistic
2 options of this multi-regime transition and considerable knowledge of both sustainability and
3 digital state-of-affairs. Yet, even if climate is considered as a key concern, there is limited
4 access to TT expertise in the cities. Consequently, there is no clear understanding what actions
5 to prioritize and what digital can bring to sustainability transition (Rotterdam, Tallinn,
6 Utrecht). This entails questions such as which digital development to prioritize for reaching
7 certain emission reduction goals. For example, should digital effort be directed towards
8 upstream behaviour, i.e. consumption, or waste management (Camden), or whether trees or
9 bike lanes are more suitable for decarbonizing (Barcelona). We also see more forward-looking
10 questions about what kind of sustainable future would be enabled by emerging digital
11 technologies such as AI or blockchain (Camden).

12 Intimately related to the knowledge resources is the question of human resources. Lack of
13 skilled staff who were capable of bridging multiple systems and regimes is seen as a major
14 constraint. Despite the ubiquitous presence of digital technologies, they are still new "things"
15 for many staff members (e.g. infrastructure planners in Barcelona or Helsinki). As put by a
16 respondent in Barcelona:

17 *We know we can design a bus route; but it's much harder in the field of energy retrofits,*
18 *mass installation of solar panels... these require new knowledge, new skills, new staff.*
19 *(Sustainable strategy director, Barcelona)*

20 Therefore, cities have resorted to hiring employees with new skills-set (e.g. Lund). They see
21 this a better option than relying on external consultants since it keeps the know-how in the
22 administration (Leuven). Recognizing that there is a need for leadership from civil servants
23 (Rotterdam), cities have also engaged in hiring high level CIOs and CTIOs to signal the
24 importance of digitalization (Barcelona). In several cities, Chief Data Officer or similar
25 innovator was hired, who knows what people and skills are required to hire further
26 employees. That said, staffing nevertheless follows siloed organizational logic and reinforces
27 the existing specialization of expertise (Barcelona, Camden).

28 Thirdly, possession of tangible assets such as financial resources was an often-cited
29 bottleneck. In some cities, while funding for innovation projects routinely comes from the EU
30 sources, acceleration and scaling is expected to be funded by local sources which is challenging

1 to secure (Tartu, Tallinn, Leuven). Cities' investments into the two areas differ considerably.
2 For example, while Hamburg spends some 85 million EUR annually on digital, it pales in
3 comparison to 3 billion EUR that the city spends on green investments annually. IT
4 developments in general are underfunded (Helsinki), and even good ideas must wait due to
5 budget constraints (Camden). Civil servants cite a "lasagna of responsibilities" in terms of
6 juggling with funding from different sources, especially in smart city domain (Leuven). Funds
7 for digital and for sustainable actions are earmarked separately which discourages joint
8 projects (Rotterdam). Cities recognize the need to stimulate private funding, which could
9 entail cooperation with private companies (Barcelona, Lund) or commercialization of public
10 data (Camden), but also stress that public data regulations, trade secrets and intellectual
11 property rights complicate the involvement of private partners.

12 A recurring constraint cited by cities is technological lag. Realizing TT opportunities requires a
13 deep digital understanding and a certain level of organizational digital maturity (e.g., Utrecht,
14 Helsinki). Some respondents noted a lack of capacity to leverage digital platforms for
15 sustainability purposes (e.g., Camden). While many cities are gradually upgrading their
16 technological infrastructure, the process is often slow and uneven. In large municipalities,
17 updating legacy IT systems is particularly challenging due to high costs and complexity
18 (Helsinki). Additionally, software offered by vendors may be outdated (Camden), and digital
19 expertise is frequently lacking in-house (Leuven, Camden). Nonetheless, there are promising
20 cases where new software applications have enabled TT innovations in urban planning,
21 transport, and energy (e.g., Leuven, Helsinki, Lund). As summarized by a respondent:

22 *Maybe in a couple of years, we'll be in a place where we are sure that we have the basic*
23 *[IT] functions running and we can keep up them in a very secure way, and then we can*
24 *start leveraging on that. /.../ then we will have the capabilities to do some innovative*
25 *added value stuff. Now we're only doing things that we need to get in place. (IT director,*
26 *Helsinki)*

27 Finally, the cities stress the importance of, and challenges related to the coordination
28 resources. New problems like green and digital transitions rely a lot on networks (Barcelona).
29 Yet, whereas, for example, Barcelona and Hamburg have involved around 2000 organizations

1 in their climate network, the depth of coordinated action remains limited. As argued by a
2 respondent in Barcelona:

3 *What is needed isn't defining common interest but defining common needs and*
4 *solutions, and common budgeting. Otherwise, it's just an MOU. (Deputy mayor,*
5 *Barcelona)*

6 Cities realize well the centrality of authority and power as important coordination resources.
7 When discussing the prospects for advancing the TT, a respondent argued that “it's not
8 necessarily about mandate, but rather about authority” (Rotterdam). At the same time, even
9 if cities have established new structures to coordinate sustainability and digital transitions
10 from one unit (e.g. Tallinn), these units possess limited power and legitimacy to enforce their
11 expectations on the otherwise decentralized city organization or wider sustainability
12 networks. Often, there is a lack of common norms and information enabling the TT
13 coordination. Teams from the domain of digitalization are (literally) distanced from teams
14 from the domain of sustainability, which makes it hard to find each other and cooperate; these
15 teams “don't speak each other's languages” (Utrecht). At the same time, all cities experienced
16 issues with translating the lessons from TT experiments into useful information that would
17 facilitate TT coordination.

18 4. Discussion

19 With this paper, we aimed at exploring how city governments couple the sustainability and
20 digital transitions. Although an exploratory study, the results point to some broad patterns
21 emerging across the studied cities.

22 4.1. Digitalization and sustainability still as parallel tracks

23 Despite the long-term framing of cities as the key venue for smart and sustainable
24 development by the European Union (Kovacic et al. 2024), city governments do not engage in
25 the long-term cultural discussions or society-wide norm setting to tilt the landscape
26 influencing the TT (cf. Loorbach 2010). Correspondingly, we can observe that city governments
27 have not developed any overarching strategic approaches to the TT. The multi-regime
28 interactions between digital and sustainable transitions are confined to various socio-
29 technical domain policies from mobility and planning to circularity and energy. Cities

1 conceptualize the TT as a unidirectional structural coupling of the two meta-regimes (cf.
2 Andersen and Markard, 2024): the digital – foremost in the form of digital data – is a resource
3 for sustainability transitions, but without adopting any general rules or routines to address
4 the systemic interactions and challenges of the two meta-regimes. While there are some
5 examples of city governments strategically pre-defining and implementing twin platforms and
6 structures (e.g. re-structuring municipal energy or mobility companies), the overall strategic
7 approach to digitalization and sustainability is still separated. The limited twinning aspirations
8 have been translated into the current techno-political environment where digital is perceived
9 a crucial – if not neutral – resource. This reduces space for exploring and shaping the systemic
10 interactions between sustainability and digital transitions. These findings provide further
11 support to recent research that questions the ability of the European public sectors to
12 integrate the two transitions beyond rhetorical twinning (Kovacic et al 2024; García Casañas
13 and Kovacic 2025), while also extending these insights to the local level.

14 4.2. Niche-level twinning serving the efficiency gains, not (yet?) new twin 15 trajectories

16 The narrow strategic approach towards the TT is reflected in three types of niche level
17 innovation approaches prevalent in the cities: *sustainability-driven*, *technology-driven* or
18 *coordination-driven* approaches. In most socio-technical domains, the twin innovations and
19 the new experimental knowledge created is yet to lead to new types of systemic interactions
20 and routines. Digitalization is still mostly used to optimize the efficiency gains of existing
21 systems. Moreover, as the new TT knowledge mostly emerges from and remain in a particular
22 socio-technical domain (e.g., mobility, energy, circularity, urban planning), there is the need
23 to develop much more effective reflexive capabilities. There are some early signs of multi-
24 system integrations that are facilitated by digital innovations (such as between housing and
25 energy; or built environment and transportation) which stem from bottom-up articulation of
26 coordination problems. As the results demonstrate, this kind of open-ended innovation may
27 lead to the combination of strategic, organizational, regulatory and technological changes
28 supported by digitalization. Although rarely used, *coordination-driven experimentation* may
29 possess untapped potential for the cities to develop and adopt new meta-rules for the TT.

4.3. Inherent limitations

Crucially, as the interviews demonstrated, despite formalized strategies, political support and ongoing investments, city officials do not expect the climate goals to be achievable any time soon. This fundamental uncertainty leads them to question whether it is necessary to consider and pursue the TT. At the same time, a bulk of TT experiments are driven by the technology-push logic, which tends to lead to isolated innovation actions with limited influence on institutionalized sustainability practices. In addition, city governments still suffer from digital and data capability gaps, which means that the actual ability to explore and exploit digital options is much more limited than expected. At first glance, this is somewhat a paradoxical finding since at the urban level the digital transition is politically much less contested than the sustainability transition. However, the limited ability to explore and exploit the digital options in the context of sustainability can likely be explained by the lock-in effects (Kanger et al 2024). For decades city governments have invested in their digital capabilities that would primarily serve the logic of mass public service provision. This has created highly complex and path-dependent digital infrastructures, which internal imaginaries and operational logics are almost completely detached from the sustainability ambitions (Meijer 2024). There is a need for critical assessment and establishment of the directionality for digitalization with appropriate accountability mechanisms that destabilize unsustainable practices (Sareen 2023).

4.4. City governments face triple, not double coordination challenge

While there have been calls for a “holistic and systemic” integration of transitions (Muench et al., 2022), our study provides empirical insight into the forms of public sector coordination required to achieve this. Supporting earlier research (Lazarevic et al., 2022), our findings confirm that effective multi-regime coupling demands simultaneous coordination and legitimation across both horizontal and vertical dimensions. Our contribution extends this understanding by demonstrating that such coordination is also necessary at the meta-regime level (Kanger et al., 2024). There is a need to search for and institutionalize meta-rules that could guide the city governments in taking advantage of the TT potential. What our study also adds to the existing research is that the multi-regime coordination requires overcoming complexity of coordination not just externally but also internally. City governments are typically complex and decentralized, with diverse units operating under distinct routines. This internal fragmentation coupled with information asymmetry and lacking common norms

1 makes both horizontal and vertical coordination difficult, even when political and strategic
2 alignment exists (Bouckaert et al., 2010). Our study indicates that multi-regime interaction
3 requires comprehensive coordination and legitimation not just on strategic and policy levels,
4 but also on administrative level. Without systemic interaction at the top level of
5 administration following the traditional public sector modes of strategic and transition
6 management (Cretuzig et al 2022), transition remains at the level of niche development and
7 acceleration at the administrative siloes, and the interaction remains haphazard, and niches
8 “splintered” (cf Finstad and Andersen 2023). Our study emphasises the need for strong
9 internal coordination between top-down leadership and bottom-up experimenting.

10 4.5. Organizational capabilities as essential building blocks for multi-regime 11 coordination

12 A holistic and systemic approach to multi-system coordination requires corresponding public
13 sector capacities. Our findings reinforce prior research (e.g., Meijer, 2024; van Doren et al.,
14 2020; Biesbroek et al., 2018) while adding new nuances. Given the importance of legitimacy
15 and top-level support, TT-related capabilities cannot be expected to emerge solely from
16 bottom-up initiatives. Central coordination is essential to align efforts, mobilize cross-sectoral
17 resources, and scale innovations. We identified five key resource constraints—knowledge,
18 human capital, finance, digital maturity, and coordination—that shape cities’ ability to engage
19 with TT. However, our study emphasizes that the critical factor is the capacity to develop new
20 organizational capabilities that enable the effective mobilization of these resources (Kattel et
21 al., 2025). This includes routines that not only explore and exploit twin transition opportunities
22 but also translate the logic of one meta-regime into another—for example, aligning digital
23 innovation with environmental sustainability.

24
25 As much of this learning occurs through innovation projects, reflexive capabilities become
26 central (Loorbach, 2010; Mayne et al., 2020). Such holistic synthesis must be supported by
27 aligned organizational structures, informal knowledge-sharing routines, TT-specific budgeting,
28 and adaptive HR practices. Importantly, instrumental failures should not be conflated with
29 failures of purpose—a common issue in public administration. As Pollitt (2008) notes,
30 balancing complex systems rarely succeeds on the first attempt and should be seen as a

1 dialectical process. Given the inertia of socio-technical regimes, scaling twin transition
2 innovations will likely take decades, even in well-resourced and ambitious cities.

3 4.6. Cities as transition venues

4 Overall, our research provides some cautionary support to the recent criticism that cities still
5 lack the needed transformative capacity to perform the role of critical transition stakeholder
6 (Turnheim et al. 2020; Wolfram 2016). In the case of TT, city governments possess far less
7 authority and bargaining power than expected by some more optimistic observers to
8 coordinate and shape new sustainability trajectories. As the city governments struggle in
9 fulfilling their role in sustainability transition, the role of digitalization in enabling it has also
10 remained limited. On the other hand, city governments have not yet put a lot of effort into
11 developing a clear strategic stance towards the TT and related organizational capabilities. For
12 city governments to effectively coordinate the TT, they not only need the strategic capacity to
13 envision the change, but also political and social mandate, sufficient autonomy, time and
14 organizational capabilities to incrementally adapt, learn and improve the specific TT routines.

15 Conclusion

16
17 Recent literature on sustainability transitions has increasingly explored the roles and
18 capabilities of the public sector at both policy and administrative levels. However, it has largely
19 overlooked the critical function of coordinating multi-regime interactions from the
20 perspective of TT. Based on an exploratory study of ten European city governments, this article
21 makes three key contributions. First, we demonstrate that digital and sustainability transitions
22 remain weakly coupled by city governments. While cities have initiated various innovation
23 efforts, these are often narrowly framed—either technology-driven or sustainability-driven—
24 with only a minority focused on coordination. There is limited evidence that these actions
25 have significantly influenced the directionality of various transitions. Second, we show that
26 cities face substantial organizational resource constraints and struggle to develop the
27 capabilities necessary to support TT integration. Third, the study offers preliminary practical
28 insights into how emerging forms of multi-regime interaction and associated capabilities can
29 enhance cities' potential to align digitalization and sustainability goals. We conclude that
30 without deliberate adjustments to organizational routines and skill bases, the public sector's
31 capacity to enable synergistic TT coordination will remain limited.

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1 **Appendix A:** Brief description of the ten studied cities

- 2 • Lund, a university town in Southern Sweden, is at the forefront of sustainability
3 transition both domestically and internationally already since the 1990s (e.g. Global
4 Climate City of the year by WWF in 2022). Situated in a lively economic region and
5 hosting several high-tech company headquarters, the city is also known as a centre of
6 (digital) innovation.
- 7 • Helsinki, the capital of Finland is the dominant city of the country. With Green Party in
8 the coalition for the second term, climate neutrality is one of the major strategic action
9 domains under the supervision of the mayor. Finland is widely considered as a leading
10 digital county globally.
- 11 • Tartu, the second-largest city in Estonia, is a university town. The city has progressively
12 embraced green initiatives and has been pioneering several green and digital initiatives
13 within the Estonian context.
- 14 • Tallinn, the capital and largest city in Estonia, was named the European Green Capital
15 in 2023. As the economic centre of the country, it is home to several unicorns. It is also
16 considered as a leading city on digitalization in a generally advanced e-governance
17 context.
- 18 • Utrecht, centrally located in the Netherlands, is one of the largest cities of the country.
19 For 2022-2026, the local city council aims to address several societal complexities, one
20 of them being the climate crisis. Therefore, sustainability is an important pillar for local
21 government organization.
- 22 • Rotterdam is the second-largest city in the Netherlands. Rotterdam is renowned for its
23 seaport, which is the largest in Europe and serves as a crucial global shipping hub. For
24 the period between 2022 and 2026, local politicians aim to work on a safe, clean and
25 green city, indicating sustainability is considered important.
- 26 • Leuven is a mid-sized Belgium town near Brussels. The city is renowned for its
27 academic prominence, particularly as the home of KU Leuven, one of the leading
28 universities globally. Much of the local economy is concentrated on spin-offs from
29 academic research, especially in the digital domain. The city has also taken CO2
30 reduction and greening of public spaces on its agenda.

- 1 • Hamburg is situated in the northwestern part of Europe and is the second-largest city
2 in Germany. As a city-state with significant political and administrative influence,
3 Hamburg is strategically positioned to manage both green and digital transformations
4 effectively. The city is strategically involved in both transitions.
- 5 • Barcelona, the second largest city of Spain, is a leading innovator in both green and
6 digital transitions. In terms of governance, Barcelona has been led by progressive
7 mayors in recent years. It has a strong emphasis on people-oriented digitalization, as
8 well as an ambitious “green” strategy.
- 9 • The London Borough of Camden is regarded as an innovative and disruptive borough
10 with a strong tradition of community engagement and participation. Camden Council
11 pursues a predominately participatory, bottom-up and socially just approach to the
12 green transition. Its conceptualisation and strategic approach to the digital transition
13 are less clearly defined.
- 14

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